

How is Trust in Information Disseminated through Virtual Communication Related to Perceptions of Media Freedom

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Abstract

In the context of today's information society, trust in information disseminated through virtual communication – particularly via the Internet and mobile networks – has become a key factor shaping individuals' perceptions of reality and their decision-making. Of particular importance is the question of how perceptions of media freedom relate to trust in information received in the course of virtual communication. In the absence of standardized mechanisms for monitoring the quality of information circulating in the digital environment, including online, and given the growing diversity and accessibility of information sources, the issue of trust in information has become increasingly pressing. Examining the relationship between perceptions of media freedom and trust in information disseminated through virtual communication makes it possible to understand how these factors interact within the contemporary media landscape. The aim of this study is to identify the nature of the relationship between perceived media freedom and trust in information shared in the process of virtual communication, considering the frequency of Internet use as one of the key channels through which virtual interaction occurs.

The study is based on data from the 10th round of the European Social Survey (ESS) conducted in Russia in 2021, involving 2,070 respondents. Data were analysed using hierarchical regression and moderation analysis with the PROCESS module in SPSS. Gender, age, education level, and type of settlement were included as control variables.

The results confirm that perceptions of media freedom and frequency of Internet use play an important role in shaping trust in information disseminated through virtual communication. The findings indicate a complex relationship that varies depending on the level of Internet use. These results may be useful for further research on media consumption and trust in information, as well as for developing strategies to enhance media literacy among the population.

Keywords

trust, virtual communication, information, Internet, freedom of media, trust in information

JEL codes: D82, L86, L82

Theoretical background for studying the relationship between perceptions of media freedom and trust in information disseminated through virtual communication

In today's information society, trust in information disseminated through virtual communication – including via the Internet – has become a key factor shaping perceptions of reality and influencing decision-making. In this context, the issue of trust in information is gaining increasing relevance. The absence of standardised procedures for ensuring the quality of on-line information, which constitutes one of the core components of the modern information environment, creates specific challenges for the formation of trust in information, including information transmitted in the course of virtual communication (Rocco 1998).

Within academic discourse, there are differing views on the importance of trust in information, particularly information distributed through virtual communication. Some researchers argue that trust does not play a significant role in the consumption of digital information (Uslaner 2000), since users are aware of the potential unreliability of the information they encounter and can freely decide whether or not to rely on it (Kini and Choobineh 1998). Others contend that the concept of trust can be applied only to people, not to computer networks or technical systems (Friedman et al. 2000; Lynch 2001; Solomon 2000), because information cannot act as a social subject and lacks agency (Friedman et al. 2000; Friedman and Millett 1997). However, empirical research demonstrates that people form socially meaningful connections with ICTs, including relationships that involve trust (Cassell and Bickmore 2000; Friedman and Millett 1997).

A significant prerequisite for the formation of trust is the presence of uncertainty and vulnerability when the trustor faces risk (Kelton et al. 2008). The importance of uncertainty as a necessary condition for the emergence of the phenomenon of trust is emphasized in studies (Doney and Cannon 1997; Hardin 2001), and it is also noted that the function of trust itself is to reduce uncertainty (Heimer 2001). The overabundance and high availability of information in the modern world actualizes the problem of trust in information, because it is trust that plays the role of a tool that helps to live in conditions of uncertainty and risk (Seligmen 2002).

In a digital society, individuals perceive reality in accordance with how it is “decoded by the latest means of mass communication (for example, on the Internet)” (Veselov 2020, p. 130). At the same time, as the Internet increasingly displaces television, the language of mass communication is undergoing transformation. Today, virtually any social interaction is mediated by the smartphone (ibid.). Under these conditions, a new form of trust is emerging – digital trust, defined as users' confidence in the security of digital systems, processes, and technologies (Connolly 2020; Veselov 2020). Closely related to this is the concept of network trust, which concerns trust formed in the context of using social networks and instant messaging platforms.

Russian studies indicate that users treat information received via the Internet with considerable caution. According to VCIOM data for 2021, approximately 50% of respondents

distrust information obtained through Internet channels (Shipunova and Pozdeeva 2022). Researchers attribute low levels of digital trust in Russia primarily to insufficient digital literacy and inadequate security in the use and storage of personal data (Veselov 2020). On the one hand, information and communication technologies (ICTs) are widely used in Russia: in 2019, 97% of the population reported using a mobile phone, and 88.6% used the Internet (Information Society in the Russian Federation, 2020). On the other hand, international comparisons reveal significant room for further ICT development: according to the ICT Development Index (2017), Russia ranked 45th out of 60 countries, and according to the E-Government Development Index (2018), it ranked 32nd (Abdrakhmanova et al. 2019).

Although many people today have access to alternative information systems, mass media remain one of the primary sources through which individuals obtain knowledge about areas beyond their immediate personal experience (Jackob 2010). As a vital source of public information and an important social institution, the media perform several key functions: they disseminate information, help citizens make informed social decisions, and provide a discursive space where people from diverse backgrounds can engage in dialogue on socially significant issues. In crisis situations – such as the COVID-19 pandemic – trust in the media can substantially influence public health behaviour, underscoring the importance of trust in information (Melki 2023).

At the same time, media organizations, including those operating online, are often not free from the influence of actors who finance, regulate, or control their activities (such as political authorities, advertisers, media owners, and sponsors). From this perspective, the media may lose their role as a platform for free public discussion and instead become a tool of information warfare (Serebryakova 2016). Common techniques employed in information warfare include: substituting or manipulating original information sources; distorting initial information; and using an “information funnel,” whereby important information is pushed to the background by an overabundance of other news, among other methods.

In the absence of state regulation of the media, the diversity of information circulating in society increases. On the one hand, this may enhance citizens’ trust in the media. Media outlets that are free from government interference are often perceived as more independent and objective sources of information. When people believe that media content is not censored, they are more likely to trust the information disseminated through these channels. Research indicates that free media contribute to a more informed and critically thinking society, which in turn shapes trust in information more broadly, including trust in online sources (Norris 2023). Moreover, in environments characterized by media freedom, people tend to place greater trust in information, while simultaneously becoming more demanding regarding its quality (Van Aelst et al. 2017).

On the other hand, the lack of state regulation can exacerbate the problem of misinformation and raise ethical concerns about the content being disseminated. An increase in unreliable information heightens uncertainty, requiring information users to independently assess the credibility of sources. Under conditions of uncertainty and the absence of standardized mechanisms for ensuring information quality, trust becomes a key factor influencing how information is perceived (Kelton et al. 2008). Research also shows that individuals who evaluate information critically are less likely to trust fake news, even when they perceive the media as free from government regulation (Pennycook and Rand 2018).

People's perceptions of how free the media are from government regulation can be a significant factor shaping trust in information disseminated through virtual communication. The relationship between perceived media freedom and trust in online information can be explained through several mechanisms.

In the modern digital environment, traditional media and personal virtual communication channels are not isolated; rather, they form a unified information system. Content produced by traditional media (articles, news reports, commentary) regularly flows into instant messengers and social networks through reposts, share functions, and online discussions. Consequently, if individuals perceive the media as free and independent, they are more likely to retransmit media content in their virtual communication. Conversely, when media are perceived as unfree or propagandistic, such content – even when forwarded by a trusted acquaintance – is more likely to be met with scepticism.

At the same time, when the media are perceived as lacking independence, virtual communication channels (private chats, closed groups, instant messengers) may come to be viewed as a more reliable alternative to traditional media sources. For example, a cross-country study found that state-controlled traditional media may attempt to undermine the credibility of information disseminated on social media (Tucker et al. 2017).

Thus, trust in the media – based on the belief in their freedom and impartiality – can significantly shape trust in information circulating through virtual communication via private channels. These channels are interconnected with each other and, at the same time, can function as substitutes for traditional media sources.

Another important factor influencing trust in information disseminated through virtual communication is the frequency of Internet use. Research indicates that digital trust is closely linked to individuals' activity in the digital environment (Shipunova and Pozdeeva 2022). People who are active Internet users may be more aware of the risks associated with false information and more critical of online sources. If such users also perceive the media as free from government interference, their expectations of reliability from these sources may increase, making them more sceptical of alternative information channels. Existing studies suggest that active Internet users are more likely to verify the accuracy of information, particularly when they believe that media outlets operate independently of government control (Flanagin and Metzger 2007).

In this study, we focus on examining how trust in information disseminated through virtual communication is associated with perceptions of media freedom and the frequency of Internet use in Russia. The aim of the study is to identify the nature of this relationship while considering the frequency of Internet use as a key factor.

Research methodology

The study is based on data from the 10th round of the Russian Social Survey (ESS) conducted in Russia in 2021. The European Social Survey (ESS) is an academic, comparative, cross-country study carried out through population surveys every two years in most European countries since 2001. The aim of the ESS is to measure the attitudes, perceptions, opinions, and behaviour of populations in more than thirty European countries (ESS Russia 2025).

The sample of the ESS for Russia consisted of 2.070 respondents.

Perceptions of media freedom were measured using the following survey question:

- To what extent does the following statement correspond to the state of affairs in Russia today? “The media in Russia can freely criticise the government” (0 – not at all, 10 – completely).

Trust in information disseminated during virtual communication was assessed using the following survey question:

- “Does communicating online or via mobile phones result in people being exposed to false information?” (0 = not at all, 10 = a lot).

Based on the response scale, this variable was interpreted as the degree of distrust of information on the Internet.

For analytical purposes, responses to the variables characterising trust in information disseminated through virtual communication and perceptions of media freedom were recorded. Responses from 0 to 3 were coded as “rather no,” from 4 to 6 as “neither yes nor no,” and from 7 to 10 as “rather yes.”

The analysis also included a variable reflecting the frequency of Internet use:

- “How often do you access the Internet?” (Never, Occasionally, Several times a week, Almost every day, Every day).

To examine the relationship between perceptions of media freedom and trust in information disseminated through virtual communication, we used hierarchical regression analysis, as well as regression analysis incorporating moderation effects. The PROCESS module, integrated into SPSS, was employed for the moderation analysis.

Variables such as gender, age, education level, and type of settlement were included as control variables in the regression analysis. These variables were coded as follows:

Gender: 0 – female, 1 – male;

Age: recoded into an ordinal variable representing membership in one of the age groups: 1 – 18–29 years, 2 – 30–44 years, 3 – 45–60 years, 4 – over 60 years;

Education level: 1 – secondary education and below, 2 – secondary specialised education, 3 – higher education;

Type of settlement: 1 – city, 2 – village.

Data were processed using the statistical package SPSS 26 with the PROCESS module.

Research results

The distribution of respondents in the ESS sample according to basic socio-demographic characteristics, such as gender, age, education level, and type of settlement, is presented in Table 1. Approximately 60% of the sample were women. The vast majority of respondents (75%) lived in urban areas. The largest educational group consisted of individuals with secondary specialised education (41.5%).

Among the age groups, the following were slightly overrepresented compared with others: 16–24 years, 35–44 years, and 65 years and older.

Table 2 presents the distribution of responses for the variables analysed. Half of the respondents (50.2%) tend to believe that online communication exposes people to false information, while only one fifth believe that this is not the case. Approximately one third of respondents (30.8%) expressed an undecided position on this issue.

Regarding perceptions of media freedom, nearly half of respondents (49.8%) tend to believe that the media in Russia are unlikely to freely criticise the government, whereas slightly more than a quarter (26.8%) hold the opposite view.

Table 1. Sample distribution of the Russian Social Survey (ESS) by socio-demographic characteristics

Socio-demographic characteristics	Share (%)
Gender	
Men	39.7
Women	60.3
Total	100.0
Age	
16-24	17.6
25-34	15.9
35-44	18.2
45-54	15.1
55-64	15.3
65 and older	17.8
Total	100.0
Education	
General secondary and below	24.3
Secondary vocational	41.5
Higher	34.2
Total	100.0
Type of settlement	
City	75.0
Village	25.0
Total	100.0

Source: Author's calculations based on ESS data for Russia, 10th round, 2021

Table 2. Frequency distributions of the analysed variables

Variable	Share (%)
Online communication exposes people to the influence of false information	
Probably not.	19.0
Neither yes nor no	30.8
Most likely yes	50.2
Total	100.0
The media are free to criticize the government.	
Probably not.	49.8
Neither yes nor no	23.4
Most likely yes	26.8
Total	100.0
Frequency of Internet use	
Never	16.2
Occasionally	5.7
Several times a week	6.7
Almost every day	4.2
Every day	67.2
Total	100.0

Source: Author's calculations based on ESS data for Russia, 10th round, 2021.

In terms of Internet usage frequency, the vast majority of respondents (67.2%) reported using the Internet daily. At the same time, a significant portion of respondents (16.2%) reported never using the Internet. The remaining respondents reported accessing the Internet several times a week (6.7%), occasionally (5.7%), or almost every day (4.2%) (see Table 2).

Table 3 presents the distribution of respondents by the degree of agreement with the statement that online communication leads to exposure to false information, according to various characteristics: type of settlement, age, perception of whether the media can freely criticise the government, and frequency of Internet use.

Compared with rural residents, a slightly higher proportion of city dwellers believed that online communication exposes people to false information.

As age increases, the proportion of respondents who believe that online communication leads to exposure to false information also rises, while the proportion of those who do not hold this belief remains lower. Furthermore, younger respondents were more likely to adopt an undecided position regarding the impact of online communication on the spread of false information. For instance, among the oldest age group (over 60 years), 23.8% of respondents did not have a clear opinion on this issue, whereas among young people aged 18–30 years, this proportion was 35.9%.

Respondents who most frequently reported that online communication leads to exposure to false information were those who believed that the media were free to criticise the government. Conversely, among respondents who did not believe that the media could freely express criticism of government actions, far fewer perceived online communication as contributing to the spread of false information.

Regarding the frequency of Internet use, the following trend was observed: up to a certain threshold (several times a week), as Internet use increased, the proportion of respondents who did not believe that online communication spreads false information also increased, while the proportion who believed in its negative influence decreased. For those who used the Internet more frequently (almost every day or every day), higher frequency was associated with an increased tendency to believe that online communication exposes people to false information (see Table 3).

Education level and gender were also analysed; however, between-group differences for these variables were not statistically significant.

Table 4 presents the results of the hierarchical regression analysis examining the factors associated with trust in information on the Internet. Gender, age, education level, and type of settlement were included as control variables.

The estimates indicate that a stronger belief that the media can freely criticise the government is associated with a higher level of distrust in information on the Internet. In contrast, the relationship between the degree of distrust in online information and the frequency of Internet use did not reach statistical significance in the presented model specification.

Among the control variables, a consistent association with distrust of online information was observed for the variable reflecting type of settlement. This suggests that rural residents tend to trust information on the Internet more than urban residents. In two of the three model specifications, education level was significantly negatively associated with the degree of distrust in online information. In other words, the higher the respondents' level of education, the less likely they were to agree that online or mobile communication exposes people to false information.

Table 3. Distribution of respondents by degree of agreement that online communication leads to exposure to false information, according to various characteristics

Type of settlement*	Online communication exposes people to the influence of false information			
	Probably not	Neither yes nor no	Most likely yes	Total
City	17.8	30.3	51.8	100.0
Village	22.4	32.2	45.4	100.0
	<i>Age**</i>			
18-29	17.1	35.9	47.0	100.0
30-44	18.6	32.8	48.6	100.0
45-60	19.2	31.5	49.3	100.0
over 60 years old	22.2	23.8	54.0	100.0
	<i>The media are free to criticize the government***</i>			
probably not.	20.7	30.8	48.5	100.0
neither yes nor no	15.3	39.7	45.0	100.0
most likely yes	19.1	23.1	57.8	100.0
	<i>Frequency of Internet use***</i>			
Never	22.4	19.7	57.9	100.0
Occasionally	23.0	29.1	47.9	100.0
Several times a week	24.5	34.5	41.0	100.0
Almost every day	19.8	31.4	48.8	100.0
Every day	17.3	33.2	49.5	100.0

Note: between-group differences are significant at *p ≤ 0.05, **p ≤ 0.01, ***p ≤ 0.001; the significance of differences was assessed using the chi-square test.

Table 4. Results of the hierarchical regression analysis of factors associated with distrust of information on the Internet

Factors	Model 1**		Model 2***		Model 3**	
	Standardized β	t	Standardized β	t	Standardized β	t
Gender	-0,05*	-1.99	-0.04	-1.83	-0,05*	-1.98
Level of education	-0.05	-2.33	-0,05*	-2.08	-0,06*	-2.36
Age	0,004*	0.17	-0.01	-0.24	0.01	0.35
Type of settlement	-0,07*	-3.03	-0,07**	-3.03	-0,07**	-2.96
The belief that the media is free to criticize the government			0,05*	2.28		
Frequency of Internet use					0.01	0.41
R ²	0.008		0.01		0.008	

Note: ***p ≤ 0.001, **p ≤ 0.01, *p ≤ 0.05.

Figure 1 presents a model illustrating the relationship between trust in information disseminated through virtual communication and the degree of agreement with the statement that the media can freely criticise the government, considering the moderating effect of Internet use frequency.

Figure 1. Frequency of Internet use as a moderator of the relationship between the belief that the media can freely criticise the government and distrust of information disseminated through virtual communication. Note: ** $p \leq 0.01$

The model presented in Figure 1 is statistically significant ($F = 3.07$; $p < 0.05$; $R^2 = 0.005$). The results indicate that the more frequently a person uses the Internet and the stronger their belief that the media can freely criticise the government, the greater their trust in information disseminated through virtual communication. The interaction effect of Internet use frequency and the degree of belief in media freedom on the level of distrust in information disseminated through virtual communication was negative.

To facilitate interpretation of the moderation effect, its graphical representation is presented in Figure 2. Using the PROCESS module, respondents were divided into two categories: those who use the Internet occasionally and those who use it every day. The relationship between the belief that the media are free to criticise the government and the degree of distrust in information disseminated through virtual communication differs between these two groups. As Internet use frequency increases, the nature of this relationship changes: for occasional Internet users, the relationship is positive, whereas for daily users, the relationship becomes negative.

According to the data presented in Table 5, the relationship between the belief that the media can freely criticise the government and the degree of distrust of information disseminated through virtual communication reached statistical significance only for respondents who use the Internet occasionally. For daily Internet users, no significant relationship was observed between these variables. In other words, among occasional Internet users, the following pattern applies: the stronger the belief that the media can freely criticise the government, the higher the degree of distrust in information disseminated through virtual communication.

Figure 2. Interaction between frequency of Internet use and the belief that the media can freely criticize the government in predicting the degree of mistrust of information disseminated through virtual communication

Table 5. Relationship between the degree of distrust of information disseminated through virtual communication and the belief that the media can freely criticise the government, according to Internet use frequency

Frequency of Internet use	Standardized β	Standard error (SE)	t
Occasionally	0.08**	0.03	2.43
Every day	-0.01	0.03	-0.51

Note: **p ≤ 0.01

Conclusion

The study found that people’s perceptions of media freedom from government interference, along with their frequency of Internet use, form a complex relationship with trust in information disseminated through online communication. Trust in information disseminated via virtual communication was shown to be significantly associated with perceptions of media freedom. This finding aligns with previous research suggesting that perceptions of media freedom play a crucial role in shaping trust in information, particularly in the context of increasing information diversity (Norris 2023; Kelton et al. 2008; Pennycook and Rand 2018). Moreover, this relationship is moderated by the frequency of Internet use.

Based on hierarchical regression analysis, it was found that a stronger belief that the media can freely criticise the government is associated with a higher degree of distrust in information disseminated through virtual communication. Further analysis, considering the frequency of Internet use as a moderator of the relationship between perceptions of media

freedom and trust in information, revealed that the nature of this relationship changes as Internet use frequency increases. However, this relationship reached statistical significance only for respondents who use the Internet occasionally. In other words, for occasional Internet users, the higher the belief that the media can freely criticise the government, the greater the degree of distrust in information disseminated through virtual communication.

These findings are consistent with previous studies, which have shown that Internet users are more likely to verify the accuracy of information when they perceive the media as free from external interference (Flanagin and Metzger 2007).

The results of this study also indicate that rural residents tend to trust information disseminated through virtual communication more than urban residents. Furthermore, education level emerged as a significant differentiating factor in the degree of trust in information disseminated via virtual communication. The analysis revealed that the higher the respondents' level of education, the less likely they were to agree that online or mobile communication exposes people to false information.

It was also found that, up to a certain threshold (several times a week), as Internet use frequency increases, the proportion of respondents who do not believe that online communication spreads false information rises, while the proportion who believe in its negative influence decreases. Conversely, for those who use the Internet more than a few times a week (almost every day or every day), higher frequency of Internet use is associated with an increased tendency to believe that online communication leads to exposure to false information.

Limitations of the study and directions for future research

Assessing the degree of trust in information disseminated through virtual communication using the question “Does online or mobile communication lead to people being exposed to false information?” has certain limitations. Trust, as measured by this question, is a multifaceted construct that may encompass several types of trust simultaneously: trust in the information itself, trust in the manner in which the information is transmitted, and interpersonal trust in the context of virtual communication.

In this regard, further research is needed to gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing trust in information disseminated through virtual communication, taking into account the complexity of this phenomenon and potentially focusing on its individual dimensions.

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